

Supplementary Materials: Chimera Diimine Ligands in Emissive [Cu(P[^]P)(N[^]N)][PF₆] Complexes

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Figure S1. The ESI MS of 6-Cl-6'-Meppy.

Figure S2. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of 6-Cl-6'-Mebpy. Scale: δ /ppm. * = residual CHCl_3 .Figure S3. HMQC spectrum (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of 6-Cl-6'-Mebpy. Scale: δ /ppm. * = residual CHCl_3 (in ^1H) or CDCl_3 (in $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$).

Figure S4. HMBC spectrum (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of 6-Cl-6'-Mebpy. Scale: δ / ppm. * = residual CHCl_3 (in ^1H) or CDCl_3 (in $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$).

Figure S5. The ESI mass spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-}6'\text{-Meppy})][\text{PF}_6]$.

Figure S6. The ESI mass spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(6\text{-Cl-}6'\text{-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$.

Figure S7. Methyl region of the ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(6\text{-Cl-}6'\text{-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ (500 MHz, 298 K, acetone- d_6). * = residual acetone- d_5 .

Figure S8. The aromatic region of the HMQC spectrum (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, acetone- d_6 , 298 K) of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-6}'\text{-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$. Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S9. Part of the HMBC spectrum (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, acetone- d_6 , 298 K) of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-6}'\text{-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$. Scale: δ / ppm. * = residual acetone- d_5 ; ** = H_2O and HOD; § = CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S10. The aromatic region of the HMQC spectrum (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, acetone- d_6 , 298 K) of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(6\text{-Cl-}6'\text{-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$. Scale: δ / ppm.

Figure S11. Part of the HMBC spectrum (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, acetone- d_6 , 298 K) of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(6\text{-Cl-}6'\text{-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$. Scale: δ / ppm. * = residual acetone- d_5 ; ** = H_2O and HOD; § = CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S12. ORTEP representation of the structure of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-6}'\text{-Meppy})]^+$ cation in $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-6}'\text{-Meppy})][\text{PF}_6]$. One set of partial occupancy sites is shown (see Figure S13). Ellipsoids are plotted at a 40% probability level and H atoms are omitted. The phenyl ring with C11 was refined isotropically as it was not possible to identify two distinct orientations; atom C100 of the methyl group was also refined isotropically.

Figure S13. The disordered structure of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-6}'\text{-Meppy})]^+$ cation in $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-6}'\text{-Meppy})][\text{PF}_6]$. Each partial occupancy site was modelled with a 50% occupancy.

Figure S14. ORTEP representation of the structure of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(6\text{-Cl-6'-Mebpy})]^+$ cation in $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(6\text{-Cl-6'-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$. Ellipsoids are plotted at a 40% probability level and H atoms are omitted. The Cl/Me positions are disordered (modelled with 50% occupancies) and one site for the 6-Cl-6'-Mebpy is shown.

Figure S15. Three consecutive scans in the cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Cu}(\text{xantphos})(6\text{-Cl-6'-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in CH_2Cl_2 solution (ca. $10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{PF}_6]$ as supporting electrolyte and a scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} (referenced to internal $\text{Fc}/\text{Fc}^+ = 0.0 \text{ V}$).

Figure S16. Three consecutive scans in the cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Cu}(\text{POP})(6\text{-Cl-}6'\text{-Mebpy})][\text{PF}_6]$ in CH_2Cl_2 solution (ca. $10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{PF}_6]$ as supporting electrolyte and a scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} (referenced to internal $\text{Fc}/\text{Fc}^+ = 0.0 \text{ V}$).